

DYNAMIC RESPONSES OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PLATE SUBJECTED TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

Finite element method along with an experimentally determined static indentation law are used to study the dynamic response of a composite sandwich plate subjected to low velocity impact. The faces of the sandwich plate are considered as two separate Mindlin plates whereas the core has only the transverse shear and normal stiffness. This model allows the including of the relative deformations of two faces under concentrated load. Experimental works are also conducted on the impact of $[0_2/90_2/0_2/FOAM]_s$ sandwich plate with graphite/epoxy faces and rigid foam core. Dynamic strain histories obtained from theoretical analysis and the strain-gage experimental results are compared in good agreements. It indicates that the theoretical model employed herein describes the dynamic behavior of composite sandwich plates due to low velocity impact.

KEYWORDS: Composite Sandwich Plate; Low Velocity Impact; Dynamic Response; Contact Law; Impact Test.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing trend of using sandwich construction in aeronautical application. This is because of the development of new materials such as graphite fiber composites, with high specific strength and stiffness. More recently, sandwich constructions were further applied in building primary structures of aircrafts such as the skin of the wing, the vertical fin torque box, etc. In the foreseeable future, sandwich construction will be used extensively in weight-sensitive structures, since it offers the possibility of achieving high bending stiffness for small weight penalty.

Many research efforts have been done on the bending, vibration and buckling problems of sandwich plates [1~7]. Others studied the same problems of multilayered sandwich beams and plates [8,9]. The problem of impact on composite sandwich structures has not been drawn too much attention although the same problem for composite laminates has been investigated by many researchers [10~14]. It is known that the damage due to low velocity impact of composite laminates is usually invisible while the damage inside

the target laminates could be serious. In aeronautical applications, this undetected damage is crucial since it may result in disastrous accident during its service. In order to estimate the impact damage accurately, it is necessary to calculate dynamic responses of impacted structure precisely, and this gives the motivation to study this subject.

In the analysis of sandwich plates, the most conventional assumption is that the effect of transverse normal deformation in the core is neglected. Thus the transverse deflection of the cross section of the sandwich plate is the same through the thickness. It has been shown [15], however, that the transverse deflections of the two face plates are different under concentrated (static or dynamic) load. Therefore, the transverse normal deformation in the core need to be taken into account. Consequently, face plates were treated as two independent Mindlin plates so that the core can resist transverse shear as well as transverse normal deformations.

In this study, dynamic response of the sandwich plate due to low velocity impact was analyzed using the finite element method. A nine-node isoparametric plate element was used to model the face plates. Contact behaviors of a rigid spherical impactor and target sandwich plate were described by experimentally established indentation laws. These contact laws were employed along with the finite element equations of motion of the sandwich plate and impactor for solving dynamic response of the impacted system. Impact experiment was also performed on composite sandwich plate. It is shown that the finite element solutions are in good agreement with the experimental results.

2. VIRTUAL WORK OF THE IMPACT SYSTEM

Let the parenthesized superscript $i = 1, 2$ denote quantities associated with faces 1 and 2 of the sandwich plate, respectively, and subscript c be expressed for the core. Referring to Fig. 1, the displacement field of any arbitrary point in two face plates based on Mindlin's assumptions can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(i)}(x, y) &= u_0^{(i)}(x, y) - z^{(i)}\phi_x^{(i)}(x, y) \\ v^{(i)}(x, y) &= v_0^{(i)}(x, y) - z^{(i)}\phi_y^{(i)}(x, y) \quad ; \quad i = 1, 2 \\ w^{(i)}(x, y) &= w_0^{(i)}(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $u_0^{(i)}, v_0^{(i)}, w_0^{(i)}$ are mid-plane displacements in the x -, y - and z -directions of face plate i , and $\phi_x^{(i)}$ and $\phi_y^{(i)}$ are rotations of the cross-section of face i perpendicular to the x - and y -axes, respectively.

The displacements of any point in the core are assumed to vary linearly through the thickness. Therefore, it can be expressed in terms of the displacements of two face plates. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} u_c &= \left[\frac{(u_0^{(2)} - u_0^{(1)})}{h} + \frac{t(\phi_x^{(2)} + \phi_x^{(1)})}{2h} \right] z_c + \left[\frac{(u_0^{(2)} + u_0^{(1)})}{2} + \frac{t(\phi_x^{(2)} - \phi_x^{(1)})}{4} \right] \\ v_c &= \left[\frac{(v_0^{(2)} - v_0^{(1)})}{h} + \frac{t(\phi_y^{(2)} + \phi_y^{(1)})}{2h} \right] z_c + \left[\frac{(v_0^{(2)} + v_0^{(1)})}{2} + \frac{t(\phi_y^{(2)} - \phi_y^{(1)})}{4} \right] \\ w_c &= \frac{(w_0^{(2)} - w_0^{(1)})}{h} z_c + \frac{(w_0^{(2)} + w_0^{(1)})}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $-\frac{h}{2} \leq z_c \leq \frac{h}{2}$, t and h are the thicknesses of the faces and the core, respectively.

The strains of the faces and the core become

$$\{\epsilon^{(i)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx}^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_{yy}^{(i)} \\ \gamma_{xy}^{(i)} \\ \gamma_{yz}^{(i)} \\ \gamma_{xz}^{(i)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_p^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_s^{(i)} \end{Bmatrix} - z^{(i)} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_b^{(i)} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

and

$$\{\epsilon_c\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{zc} \\ \gamma_{yzc} \\ \gamma_{xzc} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

respectively, where

$$\{\epsilon_p^{(i)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_o^{(i)}}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_o^{(i)}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_o^{(i)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_o^{(i)}}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\{\epsilon_b^{(i)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial \phi_x^{(i)}}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \phi_y^{(i)}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \phi_x^{(i)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y^{(i)}}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\{\epsilon_s^{(i)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w^{(i)}}{\partial y} - \phi_y^{(i)} \\ \frac{\partial w^{(i)}}{\partial x} - \phi_x^{(i)} \end{Bmatrix}$$

are the in-plane, bending and transverse shear strains of face i , respectively, and

$$\{\epsilon_c\} = \frac{1}{h} \begin{Bmatrix} w^{(2)} - w^{(1)} \\ (v_o^{(2)} - v_o^{(1)}) + \frac{1}{2} [t(\phi_y^{(2)} + \phi_y^{(1)}) + h(\frac{\partial w^{(2)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w^{(1)}}{\partial y})] + z_c(\frac{\partial w^{(2)}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial w^{(1)}}{\partial y}) \\ (u_o^{(2)} - u_o^{(1)}) + \frac{1}{2} [t(\phi_x^{(2)} + \phi_x^{(1)}) + h(\frac{\partial w^{(2)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w^{(1)}}{\partial x})] + z_c(\frac{\partial w^{(2)}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial w^{(1)}}{\partial x}) \end{Bmatrix}$$

By integrating the stresses and the stresses multiplied by z across the thickness of each individual face, we obtain the laminate constitutive relation

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N}^{(i)} \\ \mathbf{M}^{(i)} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{(i)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}^{(i)} & \mathbf{B}^{(i)} & 0 \\ \mathbf{B}^{(i)} & \mathbf{D}^{(i)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{H}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_p^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_b^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_s^{(i)} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{N}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{M}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{Q}^{(i)}$ are the in-plane stress resultants, stress moments, and transverse shears of face i , respectively, and $\mathbf{A}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{B}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{D}^{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{H}^{(i)}$ are the respective in-plane, bending-in-plane, bending and transverse shear stiffness matrices.

Since the face-parallel stresses in the core are negligible, there are only the transverse stress components left. The stress-strain relations are

$$\{\sigma_c\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{zc} \\ \sigma_{yzc} \\ \sigma_{xzc} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{zc} & 0 & \\ 0 & G_{yzc} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xzc} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{zc} \\ \gamma_{yzc} \\ \gamma_{xzc} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where G_{xzc} , G_{yzc} and E_{zc} are shear and Young's moduli for the core, and $G_{xzc} = G_{yzc}$ if the core is isotropic.

Assuming that the equilibrium configuration of the impacted sandwich system at time t has been achieved, the virtual work equation for the system at time $t + \Delta t$ is written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^2 \int_{V^{(i)}} \{\delta \mathbf{u}^{(i)}\}^T \rho^{(i)} \{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}^{(i)}\} dV + \sum_{i=1}^2 \int_{V^{(i)}} \{\delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(i)}\}^T \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)}\} dV \\ & + \int_{V_c} \{\delta \mathbf{u}_c\} \rho_c \{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_c\} dV + \int_{V_c} \{\delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c\} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_c\} dV + \delta w_s m \ddot{w}_s + F \delta \alpha = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8), the first two terms are the virtual works due to inertial and internal forces of the face plates, respectively, the next two terms are the same virtual works done in the core, the fifth term is the virtual work performed by the impactor and the last term is the virtual work due to the contact force F between the impactor and the target sandwich plate. The indentation α in the last term is given by

$$\alpha = w_s(t + \Delta t) - w^P(x_o, y_o, t + \Delta t) \quad (9)$$

in which w_s, w^P is the displacements of the impactor and the face plate at the impacted point (x_o, y_o) , respectively.

3. FINITE ELEMENT EQUATIONS OF MOTION

The finite element equations of motion of the impact system can be obtained based upon the total virtual work equation (8) following routine finite element procedures. Integrate Eq. (8) over each component's thickness, express the displacement variables $\{\mathbf{u}^{(i)}\} = \{u_o^{(i)}, v_o^{(i)}, w^{(i)}, \phi_x^{(i)}, \phi_y^{(i)}\}$ with its corresponding finite element nodal values $\{\mathbf{a}_j^{(i)}\}$, use the constitutive relations, i.e., Eqs. (6) and (7), respectively, for face plates and the core, the finite element equations of motion can be obtained by considering $\{\delta \mathbf{a}^{(i)}\}$ and δw_s to be arbitrary,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_1 \\ \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_2 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{11} & \mathbf{K}_{12} \\ \mathbf{K}_{21} & \mathbf{K}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_1 \\ \mathbf{a}_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$m_s \ddot{w}_s + F = 0 \quad (11)$$

where the force vector \mathbf{F} contains a coefficient F at the node on the face plate where it is impacted by the spherical rigid ball with mass m_s . The expressions for the mass and stiffness matrices of the sandwich plate are cumbersome and will not be given here. Details of the derivation can be found in Ref. 15. Equation (10) can be rewritten symbolically as

$$[\mathbf{M}]\{\ddot{\mathbf{a}}\} + [\mathbf{K}]\{\mathbf{a}\} = \{\mathbf{P}\}. \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) governs the dynamical response of the sandwich plate while Eq. (11) governs the motion of the impactor.

Newmark constant-average-acceleration time marching integration scheme is used for solving Eqs. (11) and (12) in this study. Thus, Eqs. (11) and (12) can be written at each time step as

$$[\overline{\mathbf{K}}]\{\mathbf{a}\}^{t+\Delta t} = \{\overline{\mathbf{P}}\}^{t+\Delta t} \quad (13)$$

$$m_s w_s^{t+\Delta t} = \overline{F}^{t+\Delta t} \quad (14)$$

where

$$[\overline{\mathbf{K}}] = \frac{\Delta t^2}{4}[\mathbf{K}] + [\mathbf{M}] \quad (15)$$

$$\{\overline{\mathbf{P}}\}^{t+\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta t^2}{4}\{\mathbf{P}\}^{t+\Delta t} + [\mathbf{M}]\left(\{\mathbf{a}\}^t + \Delta t\{\dot{\mathbf{a}}\}^t + \frac{\Delta t^2}{4}\{\ddot{\mathbf{a}}\}^t\right)$$

and

$$\overline{F}^{t+\Delta t} = -\frac{\Delta t^2}{4}F^{t+\Delta t} + m_s\left(w_s^t + \Delta t\dot{w}_s^t + \frac{\Delta t^2}{4}\ddot{w}_s^t\right) \quad (16)$$

4. INDENTATION LAW

When a sandwich plate is impacted by a rigid spherical ball, Eqs. (11) and (12) govern the dynamic responses of the impactor-plate system. Equations (11) and (12) are not independent with each other, they are related by the impact force F which is not known unless some relation is specified to link the contact force and the indentation between the impactor and the target sandwich plate. Yang and Sun [16] proposed a power law based on static indentation tests. This indentation law was employed later by Tan and Sun [10] to calculate the dynamic responses of impacted composite laminates. In this study, a similar indentation test was performed to establish the contact law for spherical steel indenter and sandwich plate.

The contact laws are given as follows

loading:

$$F = k\alpha^n \quad 0 < \alpha \leq \alpha_m \quad (17)$$

unloading:

$$F = F_n \left(\frac{\alpha - \alpha_o}{\alpha_m - \alpha_o} \right)^q \quad (18)$$

where α_m and F_m are the maximum indentation during loading and maximum contact force at the beginning of unloading, respectively, and α_o is the permanent indentation given by

$$\alpha_o = \begin{cases} \beta(\alpha_m - \alpha_{cr}) & \alpha_m > \alpha_{cr} \\ 0 & \alpha_m \leq \alpha_{cr} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

The constants k, n, q, β and α_{cr} depend on the materials of the target sandwich plate and the diameter of the steel impactor. For the sandwich plate made of [0₂/90₂/0₂] graphite/epoxy faces and rigid polyurethane foam core and 1.27 cm diameter steel impactor, their values are: $k = 1.385 \times 10^5 \text{ N/m}^{0.8}$, $n = 0.8$, $q = 1.35$, $\beta = 0.171$ and $\alpha_{cr} = 26.24 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}$. It has to be pointed out that a power of 0.8 and 1.35 are used

for sandwich plates as contrast with 1.5 and 2.5, respectively, in loading and unloading stages for laminated plates.

5. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Impact test is designed to provide for the verification of theoretical solutions obtained in previous sections. A composite sandwich plate of 25 cm by 14 cm was used as the impact target. Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy laminates was used for the face sheets. The lay-up was $[0_2/90_2/0_2]$. General plastics' LAST-A-FOAM type FR10110 foam (high density rigid polyurethane foam) with thickness of 12.7 mm was used as core material. The rigid foam was sandwiched between two graphite/epoxy faces and sent into an autoclave for a one-step curing. The curing processes were same as those for graphite/epoxy laminates provided by the vender except that the curing pressure was reduced to 50-60 psi. This should avoid lean resin content in the top face.

Fourteen strain gages where placed at different locations of face sheets as shown in Fig. 2 to record the dynamic strain histories. Seven of them are placed on the impacted side, the remained seven were located on the opposite surface at same positions corresponding to the first seven. This sandwich plate was hung with two strings at two corners to achieve free boundary condition. The impactor was a 25.4 mm long bullet-like mass which consisted of a steel spherical cap of 12.7 mm in diameter, an aluminum tail and an impact-force transducer in between. The total mass of the impactor was 87 g. The impactor was then attached to a thin rod to form a pendulum that could produce impact velocities up to 2.9 m/sec. Signals from gages and transducer were amplified by a singal conditioning amplifier and stored in a HP 5183A wave-form recorder.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 25 cm by 14 cm composite sandwich plates is impacted by a steel projectile with an impact velocity of 2.5 m/s. The motion of the impactor is along the direction normal to the mid-plane of the sandwich plate. The elastic properties of the graphite/epoxy face sheets and the rigid plastic foam are given as follows:

graphite/epoxy

$$\begin{array}{lll} E_1 = 139 \text{ GPa} & E_2 = 9.86 \text{ GPa} & G_{12} = 5.24 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{12} = 0.3 & \rho = 1.59 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3 & \text{ply thickness } t = 0.127 \text{ mm} \end{array}$$

rigid foam

$$\begin{array}{l} E_{zc} = 90.0 \text{ MPa} \quad G_{xzc} = G_{yzc} = 32.0 \text{ MPa} \\ \rho_c = 170.6 \text{ kg/m}^3 \end{array}$$

The sandwich plates was discretized by 10×10 (100) nine-node isoparametric plate elements for one quadrant of each face sheet with finer elements near impacted point. The impactor was considered to be a rigid ball. The equations of motion of the impactor-plate system, Eqs. (11) and (12), along with the contact laws given by Eqs. (17) and (18) were solved simultaneously. Since Newmark's constant-average acceleration scheme is unconditional stable, the choice of integration time step depends on the convergence of solution. For the present study, several Δt were tested. It was shown that a time integration step $\Delta t = 1.0$ micro-second would lead to converged solution. In this research, $\Delta t = 0.5$ micro-second was used in the finite difference time integration.

Figures 3-6 show the dynamic strain response histories at four selected locations. In these figures, the dynamic strain histories calculated by finite element analysis are represented by solid lines while the experimental data measured by strain gages are expressed by discrete circles. Comparisons between the finite element solutions and experimental results are very good. It is noted that the magnitude of maximum strain at point 13 (Fig. 3) is higher than that at point 14 (Fig. 4), while the magnitude of maximum strains at Points 1 and 2 are approximately same. This is due to the fact that Point 13 is on the impacted side which deflected more than point 14 on the opposite side near the impacted point. Points 1 and 2 located relatively far away from the impacted point. Hence, the magnitude of the maximum strain are essentially the same but have different signs (Figs. 5 and 6). For points far away from impacted point, dynamic responses are dominated mainly by bending effect. From this observation, it is necessary to consider the transverse normal strain of the core in the analysis in order to include the relative deflections of two face plates. Strain histories from finite element solutions and experimental data at other points are compared as good as those shown in this paper. Because of space limitations, they will not be given here.

The measured impact force transducer responses and the computed contact force history are also plotted against time as shown in Fig. 7. Practically, these two results can not be compared, since the computed contact force was calculated at the point where the target plate contact with the impactor while the experimental transducer response was picked up at its own position. Nevertheless, this figure provide a reference for the contact between a rigid ball and a composite sandwich plate. From this figure, the total duration of contact for this impact test was about 1250μ sec. Only single contact was observed for the impact of sandwich plate whereas multiple contact could happen for laminate plates [10]. The reason is that sandwich plates have much higher bending stiffness than laminated plate.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The low velocity impact of a composite sandwich plate and a rigid ball was studied theoretically and experimentally. Dynamic response of a composite sandwich plate was calculated by using a statically determined indentation laws along with a nine-node isoparametric plate finite element program. It is evident that the transverse normal deformation of the core should be included in the finite element model to demonstrate the relative transverse deflections of the faces near the impacted point. The strain histories obtained by the finite element method are in good agreement with the test results. Finally, unlike the impact of a laminated plate which involves multiple contact phenomenon, there is only a single contact between impactor and composite sandwich plate during impact.

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Fig. 1 Deformation of sandwich plate.

Fig. 2 Dimensions of sandwich plate and strain gage locations.

Fig. 3 Dynamic strain history at point 13.

Fig. 4 Dynamic strain history at point 14.

Fig. 5 Dynamic strain history at point 1.

Fig. 6 Dynamic strain history at point 2.

Fig. 7 Computed contact force and experimental transducer response.